

A Hypercrosslinked Phenothiazine Polymer as Low-cost and Durable Organic Cathode for Rechargeable Lithium Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Organic macromolecules bearing redox active units are projected to be promising candidates as safe and sustainable alternatives to the current inorganic intercalation electrodes in Li-ion batteries (LIBs). Although a range of redox polymers with various sizes, architectures and topologies have been successfully evaluated in LIBs, cost-effective polymerization routes towards their synthesis

are rarely considered. Here, a cost-effective synthetic route was employed to synthesize a hypercrosslinked polymeric network bearing a representative p-type organic redox functionality known as phenothiazine. This hypercrosslinked phenothiazine polymer (named as IEP-29) was subsequently evaluated as an organic cathode in a lithium battery. The hereby used “knitting” polymerization technique operating through Friedel-Crafts mechanism allowed us to produce the final atom-economic polymeric network. The material features remarkably high density of phenothiazines redox units connected by only allylic carbons (-CH₂-), unlike bulky crosslinkers used for the production of common hyperbranched/porous polymers. The IEP-29 cathode delivered high capacity (106 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.5 C), close to the theoretical value, high potential output (3.6 V vs. Li/Li⁺), excellent rate capability (60 mAh g⁻¹ at 15 C), and good cycle stability (79% capacity retention after 1000 cycles at 2 C). Since the hereby used “knitting” method is a quite facile method to polymerize low-cost materials in high yields, the findings pave the way of valorization of the organic electrode materials for scalable applications without compromising the performance.

INTRODUCTION

The world is facing environmental and economic problems due to the dependency on fossil fuels.¹ Therefore, transition from fossil fuels to readily available, eco-friendly, and renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar power, stands as one of the ultimate goals of modern society.² Since electricity can easily be converted to other forms such as heating or mechanical energy, production, storage, and mobilization of electricity by using green-sustainable platforms are crucial to make these renewable energies alternative viable.³

Rechargeable batteries, particularly lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), play a pivotal role in efficiently storing and mobilizing electrical energy. These versatile batteries are extensively utilized in a wide array of end-user products, ranging from cell phones to e-vehicles, making them the most popular and widely adopted battery technology.^{4,5} Commercially available LIBs typically comprise a lithium intercalating inorganic cathode and a graphite anode separated by organic-based electrolyte.⁶ Despite their remarkable performance, the mentioned combination of inorganic counterparts is reaching their theoretical performance limit, thus, further development to improve the current status is becoming extremely challenging.⁷ Moreover, there are also concerns related to the raw materials used in lithium intercalating electrodes. In particular, some of these materials are scarce, toxic, and geographically limited, making them inaccessible for many regions worldwide. As a result, research and development efforts are actively seeking alternative materials and innovative battery technologies to address these limitations and to create more sustainable energy storage solutions.^{8,9} In this context, introducing organic compounds as electrode materials is a good alternative since organic raw materials are more reachable, abundant, and easier to produce through great selection of reaction techniques and precursors.^{10,11}

The utilization of organic constituents within battery electrodes dates back to the inception of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). However, the conjugated polymers initially examined were found to be less efficient than inorganic materials due to their inferior performances, for instance, low specific capacity and poor cycling stabilities.^{12,13} Fortunately, redox-polymers bearing functional groups like carbonyls, amines and nitroxide radicals were founded to exhibit significantly better electrochemical performance. This discovery reignited interest in using organic materials as electrode components once again.¹⁴⁻¹⁷

However, organic electrodes have two notable drawbacks such as poor conductivity compared to inorganic materials and the tendency to leach out during the battery operation.^{18,19} Former is compensated by making their composites with high amounts of conductive additives like carbon black, nanotubes, etc., and the general solution for the latter is forming their larger molecular weight analogues (i.e. polymers).^{16,17} Particularly, extended (hypercrosslinked, ladder type, etc.) polymers produced from conjugated monomers are interesting to overcome both shortcomings thanks to their electron rich and poorly/non- soluble backbone.²⁰⁻²⁶

Based on the charge storage mechanisms of redox polymers, they can be generally classified into: n-type undergoing $n \leftrightarrow n^-$, p-type undergoing $p \leftrightarrow p^+$, and bipolar exhibiting $b^- \leftrightarrow b \leftrightarrow b^+$ redox reactions, with the simultaneous shuttling of electroneutralizing cations, anions, and dual-ions, respectively.^{17,27,28} In general, n-type polymer cathodes delivered high specific capacities and good cyclability, but low voltage output in LIBs. On the contrary, p-type polymer cathodes are characterized by high voltage output, but suffer from low specific capacities due to the limited active sites and large molecular weight of the repeating units.

Among the variety of p-type redox polymers (e.g. polymers containing dihydrophenazine, -thianthrene, -phenoxazine), phenothiazine-based materials are attracting a growing interest in the last years. This is mostly due to the high reversibility and fast kinetics of their redox center that leads to excellent cycling stabilities and rate capabilities of these compounds. Phenothiazine-based macromolecules in various sizes and topologies (i.e. non-conjugated or conjugated forms of its numerous derivatives, alkyl-substituted copolymers, etc.) were recently investigated as organic cathode in various battery configurations.²⁹⁻³⁴ Indeed, their hypercrosslinked/porous polymeric analogues have also been produced, delivering specific capacities close to the theoretical values considering 1 electron process (70-120 mAh g⁻¹), although slightly lower cycling stability and rate

capability,^{21,34–37} compared to linear counterparts.³⁸ Nevertheless, those polymers were mostly produced either through several steps by using noble metal catalysts using costly starting materials/monomers or consist of bulky crosslinkers which do not contribute to the redox processes (i.e. leading to low specific capacities).

To fully leverage the high voltage advantage of p-type redox polymers, including phenothiazines, it is crucial to focus on enhancing specific capacity while also ensuring cost-effective synthetic routes.³⁴ By focusing on improving these aspects, we can pave the way for the design of high-performance and practical p-type polymer cathodes that are both efficient and economically viable for energy storage applications.

Here, we present a new hypercrosslinked phenothiazine polymer (named as **IEP-29**; IEP stands for **IMDEA Energy Polymer**) produced through an easy knitting polymerization method,^{39,40} which involves commercially available and low-cost precursors. Since the polymerization is established through only one aliphatic carbon, gravimetric ratio of redox active centers to inactive linkers is very high. Indeed, such high concentration of redox active species allowed **IEP-29** to exhibit a theoretical capacity of 112 mAh g⁻¹, which is only 10% lower than the one associated to the redox active building block (10-methyl-10H-phenothiazine) (125 mA g⁻¹). When tested in lithium batteries, the obtained specific capacity of **IEP-29** was as high as 106 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.5 C, thereby achieving an impressive 95 % capacity utilization. We also systematically investigated the effect of various polymer-to-carbon ratios on the rate capability of **IEP-29** revealing that the IEP-29 exhibit good performances up to a polymer content as high as 80%. Moreover, rate capability, cycling stability and performance in Ragone plot of our IEP-29 were compared, and demonstrated to be superior than most of the state-of-the-art p-type polymer cathodes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

10-methyl-10H-phenothiazine (98%), formaldehyde dimethyl acetal (FDA, 98%) and FeCl_3 (98%) were bought from Alfa Aesar. Anhydrous 1,2-dichloroethane (99.5%, AcroSeal) was received from Acros. HPLC grade. EC, N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone NMP, isopropyl alcohol IPA, methanol MeOH, tetrahydrofuran THF, chloroform CHCl_3 used for washing, Soxhlet extraction, and electrode preparation were bought from Sigma-Aldrich. Reduced graphene oxide (RGO; Nanografi), single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs; Nanografi), 1M LiPF_6 in EC/DCM (1/1, v/v; Solvionic), Lithium foil (600 μm , Sigma-Aldrich), and Celgard (2500, Sigma-Aldrich) were used as received.

Synthesis of IEP-29

The synthetic procedure was similar to previously published methods.^{41,42} First, 0.4 g (1.87 mmol) 10-methyl-10H-phenothiazine (MePTz) was placed in a one-neck flask in glovebox. A separate three-neck flask containing a magnetic stirrer was charged with 1.22 g (7.50 mmol) FeCl_3 in glovebox, too. Both sealed flasks were then taken out of the glovebox and connected to a Schlenk line under inert atmosphere. Next, the suspension of FeCl_3 was prepared by adding 10 mL anhydrous 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE) under inert atmosphere. The flask was connected to a reflux condenser, and its exhaust connected to trap containing 0.1 M NaHCO_3 aqueous solution, all under argon flow. In following, MePTz was also dissolved in 8 mL DCE, and mixed with 0.66 mL (7.50 mmol) formaldehyde dimethyl acetal (FDA) under inert atmosphere. The solution of monomer and crosslinker was then introduced to the FeCl_3 suspension at room temperature under inert atmosphere. After 5 minutes under stirring at room temperature, during which the color changed

to dark red, the system was heated to 80 °C and stirred for 16 hours. The heterogenous mixture was cooled down to room temperature, quenched with 2 mL of MeOH and filtered. The obtained solid was washed with following solvents: 100 mL MeOH, 100 mL water, 100 mL THF, 100 mL CHCl₃ and 30 mL MeOH. Finally, it was transferred to the Soxhlet extractor to be intensively washed overnight with MeOH. The remaining solid was dried under vacuum at 80 °C, resulting in the formation of a dark brown-colored powder with a yield of 83% (0.39 g).

100 MHz ¹³C Solid-state Cross-Polarization Magic Angle Spinning (CP-MAS) Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR, in δ scale (ppm)): 144; 138; 135; 127; 113; 33. Elemental Analysis: 72.35% carbon (C), 4.63% hydrogen (H), 6.04% nitrogen (N), 12.23% sulfur (S). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR in cm⁻¹): 1465; 1330; 1256; 808.

Physico-chemical Characterization

Thermo Fisher Scientific Nicolet 6700 was used for ATR-IR measurements. Gas sorption was performed by using Tristar II Plus. CP-MAS ¹³C NMR was recorded by using Bruker AVIII/HD spectrometer (100 MHz for ¹³C). Solution-state ¹H (500 MHz) & ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) were recorded by using Bruker Ultrashield 500 Plus consola Advance III, 500 MHz against tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the internal standard. Thermal elemental analysis CHNS was conducted via Thermo Flash Smart. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was recorded by using Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter, the ramp was 10 °C/min until 900 °C either under argon or air. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis were performed by using JEOL JSM-7900F equipped with ULTIM Max 170 from Oxford Instruments.

Electrode Preparation

IEP-29 buckypaper electrode was prepared by dispersing together SWCNT/rGO and **IEP-29** in NMP and IPA solvents (1:1, v/v), followed by vacuum-assisted filtration processes, as reported in our recent articles.^{43,44} As an example, the buckypaper of 50 wt.% **IEP-29** is prepared as following: 10 mg of **IEP-29** was mixed with 7.5 mg SWCNTs and 2.5 mg RGO in 14 mL NMP and IPA mixture. The suspension was stirred overnight at room temperature, and the formed ink was tip-sonicated for an hour. Next, the dispersed solid was collected in the form of a free-standing buckypaper by vacuum filtration through a nylon filter with a pore size *ca.* 0.45 μm . Afterwards, the buckypaper was peeled carefully from the surface of the filter paper, dried overnight at 75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum. The buckypaper electrode was cut into circular discs with a diameter of 8 mm, having an average mass loading and thickness of 2 mg cm^{-2} and 73 μm , respectively. The procedure was adopted to prepare buckypapers with polymer-to-carbon percentages ranging from 40 wt% to 80 wt% of IEP-29 maintaining always the same SWCNT:rGO ratio (3:1) wt/wt. For instance, the compositions of the working electrodes were 80:15:5 (polymer:SWCNTs/rGO) for 80 wt.% polymer loading and 50:37.5:12.5 for 50 wt.% polymer loading. The mass loading of IEP-29 was 1.4, 1.8, 2, 1.9, and 2.3 mg cm^{-2} for 40, 50, 60, 70, and 80 wt% composite electrodes. While keeping the composition fixed to 50 wt%, higher IEP-29 mass loadings of 4.5 and 12.5 mg cm^{-2} in the buckypaper architecture, were also prepared by filtering higher amounts of electrode's constituents. Also for comparison, conventional electrodes with 50:40:10 (IEP-29:C65 or SWCNT+RGO:PVDF) composition were prepared by a classical slurry-casting approach using the doctor-blade technique on carbon-coated Al foil. The blade height was adjusted to 100 and 150 μm for wet slurry casting for C65 and SWCNT+RGO additives, and the obtained IEP-29 mass loadings were 1.2 and 1.3 mg cm^{-2} , respectively.

Li-polymer Cell Assembly

Coin-type (LIR2032) electrochemical half-cells were prepared by assembling a circular disc (8 mm in diameter) of IEP-29 buckypaper as the working electrode, a lithium foil as the counter and reference electrodes. The separator, a Celgard membrane, was soaked with ~100 μL of electrolyte (1M LiPF_6 in EC/DCM (1/1, v/v)). Cell assembly was carried out in an Argon-filled glovebox (MBraun) with H_2O and O_2 concentrations of less than 0.1 ppm.

Electrochemical Characterization

Electrochemical performance of polymer cathodes was assessed in a Li//IEP-29 coin cell configuration using different techniques. Coin cells were tested by Cyclic voltammetry (CV) to determine the working potential window at 1 mV s^{-1} by step-wise increase of the upper-potential cut-off limit, while keeping the lower-potential cut-off limit to 3 V (vs Li/Li^+). CV at different scan rates of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.75 mV s^{-1} was used to determine the power-law behavior ($i_p = a\nu^b$ relationship) of IEP-29. The rate performance of coin cells was evaluated by Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) at different current densities (from C/2 to 30 C, 1 C = 112 mAh/g). The cycle stability was carried out at 2 C between 3.0 and 4.2 V (vs. Li/Li^+).

As a commonly used procedure for polymer-based organic batteries, the specific capacities and current rates (C-rates) were normalized with respect to the mass of IEP-29 polymer in the electrode.

Theoretical capacity (C_{theo}) of IEP-29 hypercrosslinked polymer was calculated according to the following equation:

$$C_{theo} = \frac{nF}{M} \quad (\text{equation 1})$$

where n is the number of electrons involved in the redox process, F is the Faraday constant (96500C=26806 mAh) and M is the molecular mass calculated assuming a structural composition of 239.35 g mol⁻¹. Theoretical specific capacity (C_{theo}) for one electron process of IEP-29 was reasonably calculated to be 112 mAh/g, since it is difficult to determine the exact structure of such amorphous hypercrosslinked compounds and to keep it consistent with the similar structures reported in the literature.^{33,35,36}

The resistive-capacitive characteristics of the Li//IEP-29 cells were quantified by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and the data were collected in the 0.01 – 2 x 10⁵ Hz frequency range using a sinusoidal signal with an amplitude of 10 mV ($V_{\text{rms}} \approx 7.07$ mV) at different potentials during charging and discharging steps.

Galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) was used to determine the solid-state chemical diffusivity of PF₆⁻ ($D_{\text{PF}_6^-}$) within the polymer cathode. The pre-cycled Li//IEP-29 cell was first fully discharged, followed by the charge step at C/5 for 600 s and then left to rest for 60 min. The charging/resting was repeated until the charge voltage reached 4.1 V. Then a repeated discharging/resting protocol was applied for the discharging process until the discharge voltage reached 3 V. The PF₆⁻ diffusivity was calculated using the following equation:

$$D_{\text{PF}_6^-} = \frac{4L^2}{\tau\pi} (\Delta E_s / \Delta E_t)^2 \quad (\text{equation 2})$$

where L (cm) corresponds to the diffusion length of PF₆⁻, which is approximately equal to the thickness of electrode (73 μm; 50% polymer content, 2 mg cm⁻²), τ represents the constant current pulse duration (s), ΔE_s and ΔE_t are the steady-state potential change (V) caused by the current

pulse and the potential change (V) during the constant current pulse (neglecting the IR drop), respectively.

CVs, GITT and EIS experiments were performed with a Bio-logic VMP3 multichannel Potentiostat/Galvanostat (Biologic SP-150). The cycling and rate performance of coin cells were evaluated by GCD experiments with a Neware battery cycler at ambient temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesis of the phenothiazine-based hypercrosslinked polymer (**IEP-29**) was conducted by using knitting polymerization technique between MePTz as the monomer and FDA as the external (hyper)crosslinker under inert atmosphere (Figure 1A). The synthetic approach is simply a Friedel-Crafts reaction, and follows the corresponding proposed mechanism. Briefly, after the external crosslinker (here FDA) reacted with the Lewis acid (here FeCl₃), the formed reactive carbanion intermediate connected (i.e. knitted) the aromatic molecules (here MePTz) via electrophilic aromatic substitution from multiple sites to form the hypercrosslinked backbone.⁴⁵ Since FDA has two leaving groups (-OMe), the connections between the MePTz were established only through the methylene (-CH₂-) bridges, which provided a lighter crosslinking in weight when compared to other common bulkier crosslinkers (e.g. 1,3,5-triethynylbenzene, tetraphenyl methane).^{46,47} Several spectroscopic techniques were employed to investigate the final chemical composition of the polymer. Primarily, solid-state CP-MAS ¹³C NMR measurements were employed for structural analysis (Figure 1B). The aliphatic region of the spectrum of **IEP-29** showed the overlapping resonances of secondary carbons coming from the FDA linkers and primary carbon connected to nitrogen of MePTz around 33 ppm, which agrees with the solution state NMR of the monomer (Figure S1-4). Moreover, the small peak around 50 ppm can be assigned to methoxy groups of

partially reacted FDA, which can be defined as the end groups.⁴⁸ The resonances of the aromatic carbons were visible between 150-100 ppm, which demonstrated similar trend with the monomer. The high intensity peaks of **IEP-29** at 127 ppm and 112 ppm can be assigned to the overlapping resonances of all the aromatic carbons (C=C), with the exception of the carbon attached to the nitrogen (C-N) that shows a peak at 144 ppm. On the other hand, appearance of the small peaks at 138 ppm and 135 ppm, is an indicative of new type of aromatic carbons that arise as a consequence of the successful polymerization. Interestingly, some amount of aromatic hydrogens were observed in the solid-state ¹H NMR spectrum of IEP-29 indicating the presence of unreacted reactive sites along the MePTz units (Supplementary Note S1, Figure S2 and S3). Nevertheless, the ratio between the intensities of aliphatic-to-aromatic hydrogens changed significantly in the favor of the former since the reacted aromatic carbons do not bear any hydrogen anymore and the introduced external crosslinkers also possess aliphatic hydrogens contributing their population with the methyl group connected to the nitrogen of MePTz. Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FT-IR) of **IEP-29** displayed vibrations similar to those of the monomer, however, slight changes were observed as a result of the polymerization (Figure 1C, full spectrums in Figure S5). For example, broadening peaks of characteristic C-N stretching at 1330 cm⁻¹ and 1256 cm⁻¹ is an indicator of increased molecular weight. Additionally, the slight shift of C-C stretching vibrations from 1443 cm⁻¹ to 1465 cm⁻¹ with an increased intensity demonstrates the electronic interactions of those moieties became different after the polymerization. On the other hand, the aromatic *C-H out-of-plane bending vibrations* (region 900-670 cm⁻¹)⁴⁹ of **IEP-29** showed the presence of unreacted aromatic carbons similar to the ¹H solid-state NMR. Nevertheless, the altered behavior in that region indicate neighboring pattern of C-H moieties have changed due to the successful polymerization by showing an intense peak at 808 cm⁻¹ in case of **IEP-29** whereas

the corresponding peaks split to 858 cm^{-1} and 750 cm^{-1} for MePTz.^{49,50} Such behavior can be speculated to be a consequence of the reaction primary occurring at the *para* positions of the heteroatoms due to less steric hindrance and the higher reactivity of these specific positions for electrophilic aromatic substitution. Therefore, presence of longer linear segments are expected along the structure with some degree of crosslinking despite the use of the optimal monomer-crosslinker ratio (i.e. 2 eq. reactive aromatic carbon *versus* 1 eq. FDA).^{39-41,48} Probably due to the long linear segments through flexible methylene bridges, **IEP-29** exhibited a negligible Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) specific surface area (S_{BET}) around $8\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$. Additionally, this low specific surface area can also be a consequence of reduced accessibility of pores due to the presence of the N-methyl groups on the phenothiazine rings. In fact, other reported non-substituted analogues obtained from knitting polymerization of H-phenothiazine exhibited some accessible specific surface areas (209 & $331\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$).^{41,48} Even though *CNHS thermal elemental analysis* is not a highly reliable quantitative analytic method for hypercrosslinked/porous polymers since the reported elemental compositions hardly reaches 100% in most cases due to the factors like the high (hydro)thermal stability of such compounds, possibility of presence of unreacted end groups and trapped solvents/catalysts in the pores,⁵¹ this method can still provide a rough estimation for the degree of crosslinking. Elemental distribution showed the synthesized **IEP-29** polymer consists of 72.35% carbon (C), 4.63% hydrogen (H), 6.04% nitrogen (N), 12.23% sulfur (S) leading to a total 95.24% (the lower total value than 100% should be due to the high (hydro)thermal stability of IEP-29 limiting the full combustion and maybe confined solvents since no trapped catalyst residues were detected within the structure see Figure S6 and S7). Table S1 depicts the theoretical elemental content of MePTz monomer (no reaction) and its different possible structural variations depending on the methylene functionalization including 1:1 - MePTz:FDA (traditional linear polymer), 1:2 -

MePTz:FDA, 1:3 - MePTz:FDA, 1:4 - MePTz:FDA (quantitative full reaction). Given that the experimentally determined N content was 6.04%, close to the theoretical N content expected in a 1:2 ratio of MePTz to FDA, this structure can confidently be attributed to **IEP-29**. That being said, detected %S amount (12.23%) lays between 1:3 (12.71%) and 1:4 (12.08%) MePTz:FDA reaction. Therefore, it is possible to say that the hypercrosslinking took place up to an extent to form the non-soluble polymeric network, and the final structure is assumed to be the product of mainly 1:2 MePTz:FDA functionalization, hence the picture of IEP-29 in Figure 1A.

Figure 1. A) Synthesis scheme of IEP-29. B) ^{13}C NMR spectra of IEP-29 in solid-state and MePTz in CHCl_3 (* refers to methoxy carbon of partially reacted FDA) C) FT-IR spectrum of IEP-29 and MePTz.

Once its chemical structure was characterized, IEP-29 was processed into conventional electrodes by slurry-casting method on carbon-coated Al-foil current collector, while comparing C65 vs SWCNTs+rGO as carbon additives and SWCNTs+rGO-supported advanced buckypaper electrode

architecture for a preliminary electrode optimization (see Experimental section for electrode fabrication). These electrodes were tested as cathodes for lithium batteries in Li//IEP-29 coin-type cells. Based on obtained higher capacities, better rate capability and good cycle stability (see Supplementary Note S2 for more details) for the buckypaper electrode, we choose this electrode architecture for further performance assessment.

First, cyclic voltammeteries (CV) of a buckypaper with composition 80:15:5 wt/wt (IEP-29:SWCNTs:rGO) were carried out at a fix scan rate of 1 mV s^{-1} in different potential interval to investigate the redox processes and to find the most suitable working potential window for further electrochemical studies (Figure 2A). The potential window was initially established from 3.0 V to 3.1 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺ and, the high cut-off potential limit was gradually increased up to upper cut-off potential of 4.5 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺. The first oxidation peak started to appear around 3.5 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺, where the polymer exhibits an anodic peak at 4.0 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺ and the corresponding cathodic peak at 3.6 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺, with a peak potential separation (ΔE_p) of approximately 0.32 V. It is worth noting that the unusual split on the CV curve of the issued one-electron process should be due to some intra-molecular rearrangements of phenothiazine moieties (i.e. intramolecular charge-transfer complex formation between the radical cationic species and neutral MePTz).³⁸ Additionally, beyond 4.2 V *vs.* Li/Li⁺, a less pronounced electrochemical process corresponding to the sulphur atom was appeared. However, such potentials can be problematic either for the electrolyte or the MePTz moieties in the conventional organic electrolytes due to decomposition and irreversible oxidation, respectively. Indeed, the only example of phenothiazine derivatives reaching its second oxidation stably was recently reported for aluminum batteries.⁵² Therefore, since the characteristic phenothiazine redox peaks for one electron process was observed to be

complete between 3.3-4.2 V vs Li/Li⁺,^{33,35} we decided to establish the working potential between 3.0 V-4.2 V for further electrochemical investigations.

Figure 2. A) Cyclic voltammograms of IEP-29 (80% polymer content) at 1 mV s⁻¹. B) Discharge capacity versus cycle number at various C-rates and different electrode composition by GCD. C) Specific capacity-potential profiles of IEP-29 buckypapers with different polymer content at 2 C. D) Specific capacity-potential profiles of IEP-29 (50% polymer content) at different C rates. Mass loading of all tested buckypapers was 2 mg cm⁻².

Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) experiments in the potential window of 3.0 - 4.2 V, and different current densities (between C/2 and 30 C) were employed to monitor the rate-dependent practical capacities of **IEP-29**. Li//IEP-29 half-cells comprising buckypapers with different ratios of active material (from 40% to 80% wt.) were employed in this study (Figure 2B-D, Fi). The investigations showed that the specific capacities of IEP-29 were close to the theoretical one (112

mAh g⁻¹) even in electrodes with small percentage of carbon materials and only small differences were observed among electrodes with different polymer content at low C-rates (≤ 2 C) (Figure 2B). Since these composite buckypaper electrodes contain varying amounts (60 to 20 wt%) of carbon additives, their capacity contribution to the total capacity in the composite electrode was evaluated (Supplementary Note S3). The composite cathode that contains highest carbon additives fraction, that is 40:60, IEP-29:carbons, still achieves ~90% capacity coming from the polymer, while this contribution is augmented to 96 and 99% in 60 and 80 wt% electrodes, respectively (Figure S10c). Hence, we can conclude that most of the capacity in the composite electrodes comes from the polymer, and capacitance contribution from carbon additives be ignored. The maximum capacities achieved for 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, and 80% of active material were 116, 106, 99, 102, and 87 mAh g⁻¹ at the lowest C-rate (C/2) and 106, 95, 89, 89, 80 mAh g⁻¹ at 2 C, respectively (Figure 2B and 2C). After 2 C, there was a noticeably decrease in specific capacities, particularly in electrodes with lower carbon content. As a result, differences among the electrodes became significantly more pronounced, especially at high C-rates (equal to or greater than 15 C) (Figure S11). Nevertheless, the IEP-29 buckypaper with 50% of polymer content was still operational with a reasonable capacity of ca. 30 mAh g⁻¹ even at 30 C (Figure 2B). Moreover, when the C-rate was reverted back to C/2, nearly quantitative capacity recovery was observed for this representative composition, signifying a strong tolerance to the high currents (Figure S12). Coulombic efficiencies reached >98% at 2C (Figure S13).

To gain insights into the electrochemical kinetics of this IEP-29 hypercrosslinked polymer and to better understand its noteworthy rate performance, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), galvanostatic intermittent titration techniques (GITT) and CV at different scan rate were employed. For this purpose, 50% active material content was chosen due to its optimal trade-off between rate

capability and practical capacity. Additionally, this composition is commonly used in existing literature, validating its suitability and facilitating a fair comparison with the state-of-the-art.^{36,53}

First, the EIS measurements were carried out at different potentials during the charging and discharging steps (Figure S14). All the Nyquist plots feature two well-defined regions: a depressed semicircle in the high frequency region and an inclined line in the low-frequency. These regions are connected by Warburg impedance (σ_w), represented by a line of $\sim 45^\circ$ slope (Figure 3A, Figure S15) that provide information about the charge-transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and diffusion of PF_6^- anions in the bulk of the electrode, respectively.⁴³ The EIS data revealed lower values of equivalent series resistances (R_s) in the range of 4.9 – 5.3 Ω and R_{CT} in the range of 260 – 403 Ω in the potential region where the redox reactions occur (3.5 – 4 V) than at 3.3 V (Figure S16). Moreover, there variation within redox reaction's potential region was also minimal.

Second, the diffusivity of PF_6^- anions in the bulk of the electrode ($D_{PF_6^-}$) was determined by GITT measurement (Figure 3B). In general, PF_6^- diffusivity at each state-of-charge (SOC) and depth-of-discharge (DOD) remains high, with an average value of 3.6×10^{-8} and $5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for charging and discharging cycles, respectively.

Finally, CV measurements at different scan rates ranging from 0.1 to 1 mV s^{-1} were conducted to obtain power-law behavior of IEP-29 ($i_p = av^b$ relationship), where logarithm of peak currents (i_p) is represented versus logarithm of scan rate (v) to obtain b that is an adjustable coefficient (Figure 3C-D).⁵⁴ Ideally, the b -value of 0.5 indicates a diffusion-controlled process, whereas the b -value of 1.0 is the signature of a capacitive-controlled behaviour. A b -value of 0.82 for the oxidation process and 0.87 for the reduction process (Figure 3D) were obtained, suggesting that the overall redox response of IEP-29 tends to be capacitive-controlled, probably on account of the

combination of fast redox kinetics of the phenothiazine redox center (low charge-transfer resistance, R_{CT}) and high PF_6^- ion diffusivities within the hypercrosslinked polymer structure.⁵⁵

Figure 3. Electrochemical kinetics evaluation of IEP-29 (50% polymer content): (a) Nyquist plots at different potentials during the charging and discharging steps. (b) $D_{PF_6^-}$ diffusivity as a function of SOC/DOD (bottom range) calculated from GITT measurement (top range). (c) CVs at different scan rates. (d) Peak current vs scan rate in logarithmic scale to obtain b-values according to $i_p = av^b$.

Based on the encouraging results confirming good kinetics, the electrochemical stability of the synthesized polymer was tested by subjecting the Li//IEP-29 (50% polymer composition) cells to a long-term cycling experiment at 2 C in the potential range of 3.0 - 4.2 V (Figure 4A). The observed average discharge potential of 3.6 V was in good agreement with the value of redox

potential attributed to phenothiazine redox-center in the CV experiments (Figure 2A). IEP-29 delivered an initial specific capacity of 92 mAh g⁻¹ (82% capacity utilization), with good capacity retention of 90% and 79% after 500 and 1000 cycles, respectively (Figure 3B). Even though the average Coulombic efficiencies were relatively low (less than 97%) for the first 30 cycles, the performance was stabilized afterwards with Coulombic efficiency higher than 99%.

Figure 4. Cycle stability of IEP-29 (50% polymer content) tested in Li//IEP-29 cell by GCD at 2 C during 1000 cycles. (A) Specific capacity-potential profiles of selected cycles. (B) Charge/discharge capacities and Coulombic efficiencies over the long-term experiment.

To comprehensively assess the viability of IEP-29 as cathode material for Li based batteries, the electrochemical performance of IEP-29 was compared with other p-type materials such as dihydrophenazine, phenothiazine, thianthrene, phenoxazine, azine, and carbazole derivatives (Table S2).^{20,33–36,53,56–63} Figure S17 represents the the rate capability performance of IEP-29 in comparison to the state-of-the-art p-type polymer cathodes in Li//polymer half-cells. Our polymer exhibited a notably impressive rate performance, retaining 70% of its specific capacity at 10 C (charge in only 6 minutes). This excellent rate capability surpasses most of the reported examples

except for HPPT³⁵ and TzBz⁶⁰. It's worth noting that the rate performance of those was assessed using electrodes with lower mass loading electrodes (1 and 0.8 mg cm⁻², respectively) compare to our electrode (2 mg cm⁻²).

Figure 5. Comparison of IEP-29 electrochemical performance with the state-of-the-art p-type polymers in Li//polymer half-cells. (a) Cycling performance showing % capacity retention against cycle index. (b) Ragone plots compiling specific discharge energy versus specific discharge power. The specific energy/power values are based on the mass of polymer in the cathode. All these plots are computed by considering some of the best performing polymer cathode materials (PPTZ,³⁴ PPTZPZ,⁵³ HPPT,³⁵ P1b,²⁰ p-BrPhPT,⁵⁶ TzBz,⁶⁰ p-DPPZ,⁵⁸ p-DPICZ-O,⁶² DAPO-TpOMe-COF,⁵⁹ P1,⁶³ PVMPT,⁶⁴ X-PVMPT³⁶ see Table S2 for all the data and chemical structures).

In terms of cycle stability, long-term performance of IEP-29 was also superior than most of these examples, except TzPz, PVMPT and X-PVMPT (Figure 5A). Furthermore, the specific capacity-potential relationship (Figure S18) and the Ragone plot (Figure 5B) provides a meaningful comparison, revealing that IEP-29 stands out as one of the best p-type materials, particularly in comparison to others exhibiting a one-electron redox process. For instance, the IEP-29 phenothiazine polymer exhibits the highest specific discharge energy of 384 Wh kg⁻¹ on account

of its high average discharge potential (3.6 V) and high specific capacity of 106 mAh g⁻¹ (Figure S15). Additionally, good rate capability of IEP-29 is further reflected in the Ragone plot, exhibiting simultaneously high specific energy and power values of 382, 342, 266, and 130 Wh kg⁻¹ at 164, 796, 3976, and 12960 W kg⁻¹, respectively. This steady and high specific energy over a wide range of power values is obviously superior than the aforementioned p-type redox polymers undergoing one electron redox process. Understandably, the specific energy and power values are higher for TzPz than IEP-29 as it exhibits higher specific capacity on account of two electron redox process.

A preliminary practicality assessment of buckypaper electrode architecture was made by testing IEP-29 higher mass loadings of 4.5 and 12.5 mg cm⁻² electrodes. As expected, lower capacity values and decreased rate performance were noted with increase in the mass loading (Figure S19a, S19c, S19d), generally attributed to the reduced material activity in the thicker electrodes.⁶⁵ For instance, the capacity values at a lower C-rate of C/2 were 107, 92 and 91 mAh g⁻¹, and decreased to 74, 32, and 10 mAh g⁻¹ at 10C for 2, 4.5 and 12.5 mg cm⁻², respectively. Nevertheless, still a high gravimetric capacity of 91 mAh g⁻¹ that correspond to a competitive areal capacity of 1.14 mAh cm⁻² was attained for the highest mass loading electrode. Moreover, a stable cycling was achieved without attenuation of initial capacity for 130 cycles (Figure S19a, S19e, S19f) with Coulombic efficiencies close to 99% (Figure S19b), despite increasing the mass loading.

In addition to its efficient electrochemical performance, one-step facile synthesis of IEP-29 through low-cost monomers and a cheap catalyst (FeCl₃) make it more appealing as a p-type electrode component (see Supplementary Note S4; Figure S20-S23 and Table S3-S7 for cost comparison of some of the highlighted p-type polymers). For example, the competitive polymers^{58,60} in Figure 5, TzPz and p-DPPZ, are produced by using a reaction named Buchwald–Hartwig coupling, which proceeds via costly Pd catalysts and specific ligand combination.

Additionally, their redox active material used in those polymers (5,10-dihydrophenazine) is quite sensitive to air, therefore, its storage can be problematic for up-scaling. Moreover, another good performing polymer highlighted in Figure 5, namely X-PVMPT,³⁶ is produced through multiple step syntheses involving long reactions at high temperatures and Pd catalyzed Suzuki-Miyaura coupling, which can be considered as an economical drawback.

CONCLUSION

The synthesis of a redox active hypercrosslinked polymer based on phenothiazine, IEP-29, using a straightforward method involving commercially available and low-cost compounds was presented. This material demonstrated an excellent performance as electrode material for lithium-based batteries. The polymer exhibited high values of specific capacities with values ranging from 116 mAh g⁻¹ to 87 mAh g⁻¹ when the active material content increased from 40% to 80%. Rate capability of IEP-29 was also excellent with specific capacities as high as 106 mAh g⁻¹, 95 mAh g⁻¹, and 30 mAh g⁻¹ for 0.5 C, 2 C, and 30 C, respectively. Moreover, the long-term cycling experiments indicated capacity retention values of 90% at 500th and 79% at 1000th cycles. Such very high durability is associated with the non-soluble and highly stable nature of the hypercrosslinked polymer formed via knitting method, which allowed to execute crosslinking with very low molecular weight materials, hence the high capacity. This study paves the way to accelerate commercialization of redox active organic electrode counterparts given the used low-cost precursors and facile formation strategy yielded materials exhibiting extra durability and high efficiencies as cathodes for lithium batteries, and promising for other metal-ion batteries.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information is available online.

Some extra spectral and electrochemical characterizations, and comparison tables can be found in the supporting information.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

Any additional relevant notes should be placed here.

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